

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

Deliverable Report

WP1– Development of a Core Outcome Set (COS) for AYAs with cancer and data collection

D1.10

Study 2 Initiation Package

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- Registration number of the clinical study in a registry meeting WHO Registry criteria
- Final version of study protocol as approved by the regulator(s) / ethics committee(s)
- Regulatory and ethics (if applicable, institutional) approvals required for the enrolment of the first study participant

Publishable summary (max ½ page)

This report provides an overview of the ethics approval for the data collection phase of STRONG AYA. The attached documents include the study protocol filed with the Institutional Review Board at the Netherlands Cancer Institute – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Hospital.

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2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)

- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
- **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
- **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
- **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
- **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
- **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
MT	Management Team

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. Infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

Defining AYAs with cancer as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis², their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴.

However, survival improvement in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors, which might be due to the fact that AYA have the highest absolute excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms⁵. AYA face some distinct challenges given that they do not belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of the scientific literature, these unique issues remain to be fully recognised and addressed by the European health systems and AYAs with cancer are frequently underserved. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the integrated paediatric (“patient/family-centred”) care services versus dispersed (“disease- centered”) adult oncology

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Review Group. Closing the gap: Research and Care Imperatives for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer. National Institute of Health, National Cancer Institute, and Livestrong Young Adult Alliance: Bethesda, MD, USA, 2006.

³ Trama A, Botta L, Steliarova-Foucher E. Cancer Burden in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Review of Epidemiological Evidence. *Cancer J* 2018; 24: 256-266

⁴ Trama A, Botta L, Foschi R et al. Survival of European adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer in 2000-07: population-based data from EURO-CARE-5. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: 896-906.

⁵ Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

⁶ Stark D, Bielack S, Brugieres L et al. Teenagers and young adults with cancer in Europe: from national programmes to a European integrated coordinated project. *European Journal of Cancer Care*, 25(3), 419-427.

⁷ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

services^{8,9,10}. Up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in society¹¹.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, given their challenges to sustain health insurance coverage¹². According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to Address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

To this aim, STRONG-AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

⁸ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE). *ESMO Open* 2021; 6: 100096.

⁹ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

¹⁰ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

¹¹ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

¹² Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

¹³ Saloustros E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. *Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health* 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁴ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

1. **Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS)** specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals.
2. **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.
3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders,** in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

Implementing these project objectives are five work packages within the STRONG-AYA project:

- WP1: Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer and Data Collection (Lead: SOUTHAMPTON)
- WP2: Governance, Data Security and Ethics (Lead: EORTC)
- WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability (Lead: UNIMAAS)
- WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, Stakeholder and Patient involvement, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (Lead: E.C.O.)
- WP5: Scientific Coordination and Project Management (Lead: NKI)

STRONG-AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG-AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

5 Study 2 initiation package

The Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) is the Coordinator of STRONG AYA. As such it leads the STRONG AYA project and sets the precedent and scope of the next phase of the project, namely data collection of the COS.

There have been delays in developing the COS in order to undertake the Delphi consensus process and to decide on the appropriate metrics. As such, at present time the NKI is the other centre to have secured ethics approval for the next phase of the project. There are several important contextual factors to consider at present regarding the ethics application for the STRONG AYA project.

- 1) Consent for the use of routinely collected data in research at the NKI, as a comprehensive cancer centre, is collected at patient registration, and thus no further patient consent is required to use data that is routinely collected in clinical practice and thus is available by data desk request from the electronic health record

- 2) Amendments to our ethics protocol to add or modify elements is very straightforward. As such, the NKI team applied for ethics approval for the use of routinely collected clinical data and the use of our existing AYA study sets in the first instance. The NKI team intends to file an amendment for prospective data collection that is not included in routine clinical practice or our existing studies.
- 3) The patient consent for the reuse of our SURVAYA and COMPRAYA data is already in place and was built into the initial informed patient consent.
- 4) The project does not fall under the MWO Act (Medical Research involving Human Subjects/ Medisch-wetenschappelijk onderzoek) criteria and thus does not need to be reviewed by law by our Medical Research and Ethics Committee (MREC). Instead, it has been reviewed by the Institutional Review Board. This means that each data-contributing centre will file its own IRB (or equivalent) locally to contribute retrospective and prospective data to STRONG AYA, in line with their local institutional ethics and regulatory guidelines. This is in part why the NKI application was submitted first in order to provide a blueprint for other partners for their data collection. To meet the non-MWO criteria a study must be:
 - a. **No** predefined scientific hypothesis (as in the case of the creation of a biobank for future research) *and/or*
 - b. Persons will **not** be subjected to any actions or rules of conduct that will **be** imposed on them
- 5) The ethics applications include the set up, and use of, the federated learning infrastructure. In addition to the local ethics applications, centres much also have 1) a consortium agreement; 2) a service user agreement with our trusted third-party secure aggregator (in our case, Medical Data Works); and 3) a data processing agreement. The NKI has completed 1 & 2, and at time of writing, awaits the ratification of the DPA before data collection and sharing via the federated infrastructure commence.
- 6) At time of writing as the NKI has only applied for the secondary use of retrospective and routinely collected data, no clinical trial study number has been registered yet. As we now have the COS and the metrics, this study will be registered before data collection begins with 'first patient in' in September 2024.

As such this document will be updated accordingly to reflect the study registration numbers and approval letters for ethics in participating centres and any amendments to the study protocol.

6 Results

The IRB application for the NKI was submitted and approved in July 2023. It was issued the IRB registration number IRBd23-193 on 25 July 2023. The protocol and approval letter are attached to this report.

7 Repository for primary data (annex)

Please find attached the study approval letter and the study protocol as of 30 March 2024.

IRBd23-193
Olga Husson
Division of Psychosocial Research & Epidemiology
o.husson@nki.nl

Amsterdam, 25/07/2023

Dear Olga Husson

Your application, entitled: STRONG-AYA: Implementing a Core Outcome Set (COS) for adolescents and Young Adults (AYA) with cancer utilizing federated learning, for the use of human material and or data is registered under number IRBd23-193.

Your application has been reviewed and approved by the NKI-AVL Institutional Review Board (IRB). The NKI IRB is a board for tailor-made reviewing of non-WMO research with human material and data. The purpose of the IRB is to assure that appropriate steps are taken to protect the rights and welfare of humans participating as subjects in a research study and to safeguard ethical conduct of research concerning, amongst others, the Dutch norm for information security NEN7510 and the GDPR.

The decision is based on all the documents registered on 25/07/2023 in IRB ART (IRBd23-193) which can be viewed on [this page](#)

This application reviewed by the IRB does not meet the WMO criteria and can be considered as a non-WMO statement.

For the record, this approval letter only applies to the study as far as it is carried out in the NKI-AVL. If the study will also be carried out in other centers, you are advised to check per center whether there is a local testing procedure there.

Sincerely

Dr. A. Broeks
Committee Secretary IRB
On behalf of Institutional Review Board (IRB)
The Netherlands Cancer Institute, Amsterdam

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Title: STRONG-AYA: Implementing a Core Outcome Set (COS) for adolescents and Young Adults (AYA) with cancer utilizing federated learning

Principal Investigators: Dr. Olga Husson & Prof. Dr. Winette van der Graaf, The Netherlands Cancer Institute – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Protocol Version:

This protocol has been written and will be conducted in respect of the Helsinki Declaration and applicable national and international regulations, including those prescribed by the European Union, such as GDPR, etc.

Date: 11/07/2023

Study responsibilities:

Sponsor according to the European Directive: The Netherlands Cancer Institute

Scientific coordinators: Dr. Olga Husson & Prof. Dr. Winette van der Graaf

Study coordinator/Researcher: Dr. Simone Hanebaum

Coordinating centre: The Netherlands Cancer Institute

Writing committee: Dr. Olga Husson, Prof. Dr. Winette van der Graaf & Dr. Simone Hanebaum

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Summary

Background

STRONG-AYA is a new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults (AYA) with cancer, defined as individuals aged 15-39 years at cancer diagnosis. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-adjusted and high-quality healthcare. AYA-care and research will benefit from the collection, secure access, and integrative analysis of a large volume and highly inclusive pool of patient-centred data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. Within STRONG-AYA we will set up a value-based healthcare research ecosystem to develop data-driven, interactive policy and visualization tools that bring, in co-creation with all stakeholders including patients, novel insights into AYA healthcare.

Objectives

The overall project objectives include:

- (1) The development of an age-specific Core Outcome Set (COS) for AYAs with cancer (in process, approved by Southampton Ethics Committee/IRB 78653. Expected draft COS: December 2023);
- 2) The Implementation of the COS in 5 national healthcare systems (France, Italy, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Poland) and establishment of national infrastructures for the collection and management of outcome data;
- 3) The enactment of a pan-European STRONG-AYA ecosystem, including a privacy-preserving federated learning infrastructure;
- 4) The dissemination of the COS and its insights gleaned from the development of bespoke analytical tools to a wide range of local and pan-European stakeholders to use real world insight to develop data driven, value-based care and research across the continent.

This IRB protocol concerns itself with objective 2 and is intended to operate as an umbrella or ‘master’ protocol for this objective at the pan-European level.

Procedure and aims

The primary aim of the STRONG-AYA consortium is to develop outcome prediction models (prevalence/incidence of, risk factors for and mechanisms of poor outcomes) for AYAs with cancer through the creation of national and pan-European federated learning infrastructure ecosystems.

Once the draft COS has been finalised (December 2023), the COS will be implemented as a research instrument to gain real-world insight from AYA data (retrospective and prospective clinical and registry data, where relevant) and into clinical practice (prospective) by building a European healthcare research ecosystem for AYA with cancer. More specifically, we aim to develop outcome prediction models (prevalence/incidence of, risk factors for and mechanisms of poor outcomes) for AYA with cancer through the method of Federated Learning (FL). These models mean that analysis is based on data from patients aged 15-39 years at primary cancer diagnosis across multiple international centres,

without any individual level patient data leaving the institution it originates from, therefore preserving patient data privacy.

Conclusion

We hypothesise that robust and generalisable FL can be developed across centres, and that this method will provide statistical models that explain the data, and demonstrate clinically useful risk factors for good and bad cancer outcomes. By linking multiple international centres, the FL models can be developed using the largest available cohort of AYA cancer patients to further develop research into AYA cancer and to better inform the care of this underserved cancer population. This has previously and recently been successful done for lung cancer patients (IRBd21-026_29-01-2021) and anal cancer patients (IRBd21-166_06-08-2021).

1 BACKGROUND

In any healthcare system it is essential that patients have access to high-quality care and to deliver tangible improvements in outcomes encompassing survival, health-related quality of life (HRQoL), the ability to attend school or work, get and raise children and actively participate in society [1]. This is particularly important for adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer, defined as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis [2]. Their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers) [3]. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates and in AYA's even over 80% will survive long-term (>5 years) [4], **However, despite the relatively favourable cancer prognosis, AYA cancer patients are at risk of treatment related development of medical effects (e.g., cardiovascular disease or second malignancies), infertility or psychosocial effects (e.g., difficulty in romantic relationships, financial toxicity due to unemployment without a prior career job), and have an increased risk of late mortality [5, 6].**

AYAs with cancer are distinct from the paediatric (<15 years) and the older adult (>40 years) cancer populations illustrated by the following findings [2, 7]:

- Their unique spectrum of cancer types (epidemiology), with both paediatric-type and adult-type tumours [8]. The AYA group faces an overlap with paediatric tumours (brain tumours, sarcoma, leukaemia and lymphoma), but also with tumours common at older age (breast and increasingly colorectal cancer), and diagnoses which typically peak at AYA age (testicular cancer, thyroid cancer and melanoma). Hence, both paediatric oncologists' input and adult oncologists' competences are needed to deliver optimal care and treatment for AYAs.
- Differences in tumour genomic, biology and clinical behaviour in AYA tumours compared to children and older adults [8, 9]. Age-specific molecular features are increasingly seen as therapeutically relevant. The biology of the host may also differ according to age, with distinct pharmacology and potential impact on therapy efficacy and toxicity profiles. Just translating the clinical management of children or older adults into the standards for the treatment of AYAs thus seems to be unjustified.
- A lack of awareness that cancer may occur in this age group (among general population and healthcare professionals (HCPs)), with often results in diagnostic delays and/or difficult access to specialised care, potentially resulting in poor survival outcomes [10]; Diagnostic delay also has a negative impact on patients' trust in the healthcare system and psychosocial outcomes such as anxiety.
- A lack of AYA cancer patients' participation in clinical protocols (reported rate of entering clinical trials ranged from 5% to 34% in published series), limiting the evidence base for treatments [11];
- Adolescence and young adulthood are complex phases of life due to the many physical, emotional, cognitive, and social transitions [12]. Important developmental tasks need to be achieved, such as forming one's own identity and a healthy body image, establishing autonomy, responsibility and independence, finishing education and starting a career, starting a romantic relationship and having and raising young children [12]. A cancer diagnosis challenges AYAs' abilities to achieve these developmental milestones [13]. The way in which AYA with cancer adjust to their cancer experience might have life-long implications for the quality of their survival [14]. Life-long consequences of treatment are often not part of the

primary treatment discussions where the strong focus is on optimal survival outcomes. Examples of themes that AYA cancer patients would prefer to be discussed already very early after diagnosis are fertility, education and work, romantic relationships and sexuality, raising young children and financial consequences of disease and treatment. All topics that are not part of standard clinical consultations, due to lack of awareness, routine (as AYA cancer patients are rare), time constraints and lack of knowledge and supportive staff to discuss and act on these issues.

- Historically, there was a lack of improvement in survival rates as compared to other age groups. For some tumour types, such as brain tumours and sarcomas, survival in AYA is still poorer than in children with the same disease [15] which is tumour biology, patient and treatment related.

A MISSED CHANCE AND UNMET NEED:

The unique characteristics require access to oncology services which provide expert cancer care and consider AYAs' age-specific and complex psychosocial and physical needs regarding (1) physical changes, development of self-image, identity, relationships, sexuality and independence; (2) age-appropriate information and communication, shared decision-making, compliance and treatment adherence; (3) privacy and peer-support; (4) peculiar behaviours of this age and risk-taking (including alcohol/substance abuse). However, in many parts of the world, AYAs with cancer face inequities of care as they are poorly served by the traditional dichotomy of the integrated paediatric ("patient/family-centred") care services versus dispersed ("disease-centred") adult oncology services [11, 16, 17]. Up to half of AYA with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in the society [18].

Cancer at AYA age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer, but the rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved; the decreased productivity and HRQoL due to the impact of the disease during formative years and long-term complications or disabilities [19]. The AYA Working Group (WG) of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe) concluded in 2021 that finding rapid solutions to 'speak the same language' among healthcare professionals (HCPs) is essential to further improve health outcomes for AYAs [11]. The WG reported that standard clinical trial endpoints, such as five-year overall survival, progression-free survival, and cancer-specific survival, often do not address the specific needs of the AYA population. The WG found a widespread geographic variation, nationally and internationally, in AYA care programs with an unstructured, often merely philanthropic, funding [11]. When ESMO and SIOPE members were asked if their patients had access to specialized services for AYA with cancer, or if such services were in development, only 33% confirmed that they had, namely: 13% in Eastern and South-Eastern Europe, 45% in Western Europe and 60% in Northern Europe [20]. In addition, substantial inequalities in support by specialised HCPs, such as psychologists, social workers, physiotherapists, dieticians and AYA-dedicated nurses were found between AYA care programs [20]. The WG also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control [11]. In 2016, the NCI updated the AYA cancer progress review group report and examined scientific gaps and opportunities for future AYA oncology [22]. It was concluded that

one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to address the burden of cancer in AYA [22].

STRONG-AYA seeks to take up this call from the ESMO-SIOPE WG and NCI to establish a core outcome set (COS), and to use real-world data, pooled in a federated learning infrastructure, to comprehensively assess patients' age-specific needs, screen for physical and psychosocial problems and provide multidisciplinary, holistic, age-specific hospital and community support. By evaluating AYA cancer patients' healthcare experiences and outcomes we believe their care and outcomes can be improved and unjustified variations in quality of care reduced. We believe that this can be done by maximizing the potential of multi stakeholders' data. Although an ever increasing amount of data is available, the collection, access, processing, and use of these data are still very fragmented within and especially across national health systems. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer. The development and implementation of a COS, a consensus-based agreed minimum set of outcomes that should be measured and reported, with patient-centred outcomes of value for AYAs with cancer, represents an opportunity to enable data-driven healthcare innovation and serve as a basis to address clinically relevant questions for this vulnerable patient group.

The creation of STRONG-AYA as a **new dedicated, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network**, consisting of AYAs with cancer, HCPs working in this field, researchers and policy-makers, builds on previous initiatives, such as the European Network for Cancer Research in Children and Adolescents program (ENCCA), a specific European Network for Teenagers and Young Adults with Cancer (ENTYAC; EU FP7 2011-14).

STRONG-AYA: We have united a network of professionals (HCPs and scientists) and patients, some of which are already collaborating within ENTYAC and the ESMO/SIOPE AYA WG, who collectively expressed their wish to join forces to work on the specific challenges of AYA with cancer. The time is right to make a significant investment to sustainably align research and healthcare to inform individual decision-making and healthcare policy. By creating **five national ecosystems and an overall European AYA healthcare research ecosystem**, concentrating on the dynamic generation and use of outcome data by all important actors within healthcare and research, we will work towards the most effective, affordable and sustainable value-based care for AYA with cancer to maximize their health outcomes.

Within STRONG-AYA we will make use of federated learning to implement the COS and create the national and pan-European ecosystem. Conventional data analysis requires sharing and centralization of data. But, combining data originating from multiple sources is difficult because of ethical, administrative, legal, and political barriers associated with data sharing [23]. In order to avoid these issues, we will use a hybrid model of centralised and federated analysis or learning techniques. Centralised approaches will mainly be applied in the local ecosystems, while federated approaches are specifically relevant for learning between ecosystems at a pan-European and the national level. Federated analysis/learning is an Artificial Intelligence technique – i.e. machine learning – that reformulates conventional data analysis algorithms so that data centralization becomes unnecessary and consequently data transfer and associated agreements are not needed [24]. Federated analysis/learning is defined as analysing or learning from data without data leaving the source: algorithms iteratively analyse separate data sources (sites) and only aggregated statistics are

produced as outputs with the outside world [24]. In other words: research questions and answers are shared between the databases instead of the data. Federated analysis/learning is a sustainable approach for AYA data as it offers a privacy-preserving solution to combine dispersed data to yield orders of magnitude more data than traditional approaches [24]. The federated analysis/learning methodology requires and forced the development of data with semantic interoperability: FAIR data [25]. An advantage of federated analysis/learning is that it makes implementation of models in daily clinical practice possible (e.g. clinical decision support systems for diagnostic decision-making), thereby facilitating a rapid learning healthcare practice [26].

2 STUDY OBJECTIVES

The primary aim of the STRONG-AYA consortium is to develop outcome prediction models (prevalence/incidence of, risk factors for and mechanisms of poor outcomes) for AYAs with cancer through federated learning (FL). These models will inform further AYA cancer research and establish best practice in care. The FL method will describe and model the relationships between the key elements of data from patients aged 15-39 years at primary cancer diagnosis across multiple international centres under their local, valid ethical approval. The FL method enables the research team to achieve this without any individual level patient data leaving the institution it originates from, therefore preserving patient data privacy. The scope of this protocol is, jointly, the collection of data determined by the COS development and the building and implementation of the STRONG AYA FL infrastructure at the NKI. At ime of IRB submission (July 2023) we currently intend to apply to only collect data as confined by the TADP. If or when data beyond the TADP is desired for STRONG AYA, a new protocol or amendment (in accordance to IRB guidelines) will be developed.

The following is required to reach the aforementioned objectives:

1. Establish a COS of outcomes and variables for data collection and measurement
 - This is in progress and the draft COS is expected to be completed by the end of 2023. The COS is being developed via a systemic literature review, qualitative interviews with patients, HCPs, and caregivers, and a consensus-building Delphi process. This process is defined by the protocol paper and ethics approval (78653) of the part of the STRONG-AYA study defining the COS based primarily at the University of Southampton. This protocol outlined the scope and need for a COS; assembled a working group; developed a study protocol encompassing a systemic literature review, qualitative interviews and a Delphi study in alignment with the EU CAYAS NET study (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/org-details/997929890/project/101056918/program/43332642/details>) to build multi-stakeholder consensus; as well as metrics and case-mix variables. Refinement of the draft COS will take place after 2023.
2. Establish national ecosystems in each of the five participating countries (Netherlands, United Kingdom, France, Italy, and Poland), consisting of
 - a) An interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder AYA cancer network of experts to facilitate collaboration, dissemination and communication, as well as the day-to-day collection of AYA patient data via routine clinical care in electronic health records (EHRs), validated patient-reported outcome (PRO) questionnaires, etc.
 - b) A technical infrastructure and tools for data management that use federated learning in line with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles (In progress, currently defined by the Data Management Plan, technical blueprint, and developing operational plans for the various ecosystems). It is envisioned that this technical infrastructure will include integrated web-portals with various and appropriate levels of access and permissions for use by various stakeholders including HCPs, patients, and policymakers

- c) A governance model and legal and framework to ensure compliance with European and each country's legal and policy stipulations regarding the collection, use and sharing of health outcomes data (e.g. robust data protection and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance)
 - d) Secure and locally controlled data warehouses of local data resources that individual partners are able to access solely by themselves as independent institutions, such as:
 - research databases,
 - clinical trials case reports,
 - cancer registries,
 - hospital-based electronic health records,
 - repositories of patient (or self) reported outcomes, and
 - other such databases that the Partner deems relevant for the STRONG-AYA
 - e) Sustainability model plan to ensure long-term sustainability of the ecosystems to support European/national/regional/local cancer policy organisations to build appropriate AYA cancer services
3. In parallel, to establish a pan-European umbrella ecosystem to manage consistency and interoperability across national ecosystems, to serve as a European gateway, and to support the creation of ecosystems in other European countries.
 4. To conduct the following activities when the national ecosystems become operational:
 - a) Retrospective data (mainly clinical) will be collected from national and regional registries or previously conducted ethically approved population-based studies, this means data have to be standardized and mapped on a common data model to integrate them in the infrastructure to be used for analysis and outcome reports.
 - b) Prospective COS data (clinical and patient-reported) will be newly collected in participating clinical centres among newly diagnosed AYA with cancer;
 - c) Retrospective COS data (clinical and patient-reported) will be collected in participating clinical centres (survivors);

We hypothesise that robust and generalisable federated models can be developed across countries, and that these models will demonstrate clinically useful prevalence/incidence rates, risk factors and mechanisms of poor outcomes as defined in the COS. By linking multiple international centres, the federated models can be developed using the largest available cohort of AYA cancer patients.

Project timelines:

WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation,

Of note for the implementation of data collection:

WP1: The systemic literature review started in November 2022 and is currently in the final stages of data extraction as of June 2023. The process whittled down over 17.000 articles to just under 3.000 for data extraction. Qualitative interviews with patients, HCPs and caregivers started in May 2023 and will shortly conclude (June 2023 – Southampton IRB 78653, see appendix). These were conducted to support the development of the COS, as well as early identification of the technical functionality desired from the STRONG AYA infrastructure. A multi-stakeholder Delphi process will start in September 2023 and conclude in late autumn in 2023 to finalise the COS. Each data collection centre must complete its internal IRB applications and gain approval and follow any local ethical procedures and regulations before data collection can begin at various centres. Collection of data will be rolling subject to the completion

of legal and regulatory requirements for the operation of the infrastructure, the collection of retrospective and prospective clinical data, integration of registry data, and the capacity to collect PROs.

WP2: A business architecture considering the technical, ethical, and legal requirements to operate the STRONG AYA ecosystems has been produced (see appendix). The first iteration of a dynamic pan-European ROPA and DPIA has been finalised and circulated to DPOs for review and signature by each consortium member (June 2023 – see appendix). Next steps include developing the formal ethical guidance and governance toolkit, including a code of conduct, for all consortium members (September 2023). Each data collection centre must also complete local ROPA and DPIAs before data collection can commence (in place by December 2023). A Joint Controllorship Agreement among STRONG AYA consortium members will be drawn up and signed as well before any data analysis will commence.

WP3: The technical infrastructure has been set up at the NKI already and currently holds synthetic data for functionality testing purposes. Basic functionality tests started in February 2023 using synthetic data and virtual machines owned by Maastricht University. Leeds Teaching Hospital, Leon Berard and possibly IGR are expected to be set up and connected with synthetic data by September, with the anticipation that the rest of the consortium will follow suit in Q4 of 2023. The Data Management Plan is in place (see appendix) and has been reviewed by each centre's DPOs and the technical blueprint has been completed as well (see appendix). A software sustainability plan for Vantage6 (owned and developed by IKNL and used in other federated learning projects that the AvL-NKI has been involved with in the past) is also in place and an in-depth internal ROPA and DPIA have been conducted at IKNL for Vantage6.

WP4: The first iteration of the operational plans for each national ecosystem is currently underway and will be complete by the end of July. The pan-European operation plan will be in place in Q4 of 2023. These are being closely developed alongside the technical experts in WP3. Discussions around the sustainability of the infrastructure will commence in July 2023.

3 STUDY DESIGN AND METHODS

Study Design & Patient Population:

This will be a mixed method observational cohort study with a retrospective and prospective part of COS data collection to investigate outcomes of AYA with cancer. All AYA aged 15-39 years at initial cancer diagnosis are eligible to be included in the study. No exclusion criteria are defined.

Data collection will take place at three levels:

1. Retrospectively by use of available national and regional registry data or previously conducted population-based studies
2. Retrospectively in clinical practice in STRONG-AYA participating centres among patients in follow-up (survivors);
3. Prospectively in clinical practice in STRONG-AYA participating centres among newly diagnosed AYA with cancer;

For ad 2 and 3: In the participating countries, AYA with cancer can be invited by their treating HCP or via a national patient organisation. Patients will be invited to participate after diagnosis (ad 3) or around a follow-up consult (ad 1) in the respective centres to enable the evaluation of the impact of cancer diagnosis, treatment and care on short- and long-term outcomes. Several centres among the consortium have already set-up such a data collection approach.

From all AYA with cancer diagnosed in the STRONG-AYA centres, we expect that the prospective part (ad 3) of STRONG-AYA will be available to around 4000 patients each year (please see the Table below under sample size) that will be followed longitudinally over time (each year). This number will only grow when STRONG-AYA will open in other countries. When patient inclusion for the prospective part of the data collection is not possible directly after diagnosis, it is also possible to include patients or survivors later in their patient journey (ad 1 – retrospective clinical practice).

With regard to ad 1 (retrospective registries/population-based study data): As an important step towards the development of future personalised prediction models, STRONG-AYA will also utilise data from the existing databases available within its consortium (e.g. in The Netherlands: clinical data from the Netherlands Cancer Registry and patient-reported outcomes via the PROFILES registry of over 4000 AYA who were diagnosed with cancer 5-20 years ago, and the SURVAYA study dataset (IRBd18-122); in UK: clinical data from the National Cancer Registry). Subject data shall be extracted and curated within the secure trusted informatics research infrastructure, inside each participating centre, in line with their local IRB requirements and national regulations.

Sample size:

This is non-randomized observational study with open questions pertaining to AYA cancer, their care, and survivorship. The question of what sample size is needed will be dependent upon on the specific sub-question, e.g., what factors affect HRQoL of AYAs vs investigating the average rates of chemotherapy in Italy versus rest of Europe. As such, lines of inquiry stemming from STRONG-AYA analyses will include an estimate of the uncertainty and potential confounding of the result rather than to pre-calculate a sample size beforehand already knowing the answer (effect size) we are trying to prove.

4 Data Items and Outcomes

Data collection and completeness

Relevant patient data will be identified and extracted from existing research and clinical databases. We encourage that data extraction from databases is carried out in a fashion which is as automated as possible. Each participating centre will be responsible for ensuring good data quality by spot checking all extracted data, in order to identify any outliers and make sure the coding system used is correct, according to the data code book provided.

Data items are classified as either “essential” or “optional”. For “essential” data items, centres should aim for at most 10% missing data for any given data item across their study cohort. Local investigators are encouraged to contact the study coordinator for further discussion if they find any specific “essential” items generally unavailable. For “optional” data items, missing data will be accepted. In order to ensure patient data privacy is preserved, a minimum of 50 patients per centre should be included.

The outcomes are defined in the COS for AYAs with cancer as part of the aforementioned work at the University of Southampton (Southampton IRB 78653). This will be available in detail in January 2024 after a consensus building Delphi process. It will consist of specific PRO variables, treatment toxicities that are important to patients and public health, treatment burden upon patients, carers and healthcare providers, risk factors for inequity of outcome such as social factors, and clinical information such as cancer extent, treatment given, cancer control status and survival status. In regard to PRO data, this protocol in its current format will use PROM data collected in daily clinical practice first, next to the data already collected in two previous studies based in the van der Graaf/Husson research group: SURVAYA (IRBd18-122/ M19VAY)/COMPRAYA (M20COM). If or when PRO data beyond the outcomes collected as part of clinical care and previous studies are desired for STRONG AYA in accordance with our finalised COS, a new protocol or amendment (in accordance to IRB guidelines) will be developed.

After consultation with an external steering committee of experts, it is anticipated that the COS will likely include a to-be-determined combination of the variables listed below, with the caveat that this list should not be taken as the final and definitive declaration of the finalised COS data set. Full definitions and coding of data items will be shared when the COS is finalized.

Patient, tumour and treatment characteristics

Essential

- Sex
- Age at primary cancer diagnosis
- Country of residence
- Tumour type
- Stage (TNM classification)
- Metastases (TNM classification)
- Treatment

Optional

- Comorbidities (pre-existing and not effects of treatment)
- Partner status
- Educational level
- Socioeconomic status
- Migration background/ ethnicity

Outcomes

Essential

- Mortality/ survival
- Incidence

Optional

- Blood and lymphatic system outcomes
- Cardiac outcomes
- Congenital, familial and genetic outcomes
- Endocrine outcomes
- Ear and labyrinth outcomes
- Eye outcomes
- Gastrointestinal outcomes
- General outcomes
- Hepatobiliary outcomes
- Immune system outcomes
- Infection and infestation outcomes
- Injury and poisoning outcomes
- Metabolism and nutrition outcomes
- Musculoskeletal and connective tissue outcomes
- Outcomes relating to neoplasms: benign, malignant and unspecified (including cysts and polyps)
- Nervous system outcomes
- Pregnancy, puerperium, and perinatal outcomes
- Renal and urinary outcomes
- Reproductive system and breast outcomes
- Psychiatric outcomes
- Respiratory, thoracic and mediastinal outcomes
- Skin and subcutaneous tissue outcomes
- Vascular outcomes
- Physical functioning
- Social functioning
- Role functioning
- Emotional functioning/well-being
- Cognitive functioning
- Global quality of life
- Perceived health status
- Delivery of care
- Personal circumstances
- Economic
- Hospital
- Need for further intervention
- Societal/ carer burden
- Adverse events/effects

Protocol version 1.0

5 Data flows and federated learning infrastructure

Following a similar rationale to [the atomCAT2 study](#), sharing data insight and cooperation in multi-centre studies is invaluable for the development and validation of prognostic models in rare cancers, which by definition encompass all AYA cancers. Federated learning infrastructures and the data flow principles behind it ensure data insights can be shared whilst preserving patient privacy and local autonomy over data. Furthermore, the agile nature of federated learning allow insights to be drawn whilst working with, not against, the diverse local contexts and situations around data collection at each participating centre.

Data flows:

Data flows within the STRONG-AYA consortium, and at the NKI, will follow the following principles:

Each Partner controls and operates its own national or local ecosystem. This is expected to consist of, but is not exclusively limited to, local data resources that the Partner is able to access solely by themselves as independent institutions, such as:

- research databases,
- clinical trials case reports,
- cancer registries,
- hospital-based electronic health records,
- repositories of patient (or self) reported outcomes, and
- other such databases that the Partner deems relevant for the STRONG-AYA as per the COS

These “grassroots” data sources are allowed to be either retrospective, or prospective, or a mixture of both. Since each Partner owns, controls and operates in their own space, they will autonomously decide when and which Data to make accessible for Federated Learning through the STRONG-AYA consortium. There is no intellectual, technical or consortium-derived mandatory requirement on every Partner to make all Data completely accessible at exactly the same time; noting, as mentioned above, that the data collection paradigm must allow for dynamism, adaptability and step-by-step accumulation (and maturation) of the Data over time.

Each Partner will be responsible for requesting individual-level subject data from primary data sources within their own area of control (as above, the electronic health records, cancer registries, etc. etc.) using local governance mechanisms and technical instruments that are feasible for the Partner. These mechanisms and instruments may, for illustration purposes only, include Data Transfer Agreements between themselves and national cancer registries, and customized data extraction tools from electronic health records hosted in their local hospital (see, for a purely illustrative example, Figure 1 below). Existing governance and instruments should be re-used wherever possible, with a view to grow and sustainably reach a better quality of data collection over time.

Figure 1: data flows for STRONG AYA

Each Partner stores pseudonymized data they have extracted from their local sources into a secured computation device which is within their institutional data security firewall. This device resides on a sub-network that can be insulated from other mission-critical and operational systems used by the institution. The Partner needs to ensure sufficient security for the private data in their own collection, using the advice of their local data protection officers and information security teams. If a Partner uses pseudonym keys to link information of the same human subject from multiple data sources, such key files must be stored on a separate device from the Data itself.

Traditionally, machine learning models are trained on data that are collected centrally from multiple sources. However, the ethical, legal and societal implications regarding sharing of data outside the source organization has led to a paradigm shift in how machine learning models are trained. Instead of sharing data, algorithms are sent to each of the data sources, where they are trained locally. The locally trained algorithms are aggregated to develop a global model in a manner as if the algorithm is trained by traditional approaches. The privacy and confidentiality of data is protected at the source and only necessary analysis is shared.

Federated learning

Figure 2: Principle parts of federated learning

STRONG-AYA will use the Personal Health Train (PHT) paradigm to create its federated learning infrastructure. The Personal Health Train (PHT) is a privacy-by-design infrastructure for performing federated/distributed machine learning. The data providers (hospitals) can participate in multicentre data analysis without exposing sensitive data outside the organization. The principle of PHT can co-exist with other privacy enhancing measures such as encrypted and perturbed data, but the crucial point here is that the PHT paradigm never relies solely on the unbreakability of encryption nor the irreversibility of perturbation to safeguard patient privacy. PHT ensures that the machine learning process is completed in a data agnostic manner. The data station provides an execution platform for the algorithm and provides secure access to the data repository. In the PHT infrastructure, the metaphor ‘train’ refers to the Docker containers containing the data query and the algorithm. These containers provide an isolated and secure environment for the query and algorithm. ‘Tracks’ are the secured communication channels connecting the central message broker, the researcher and the data stations. Trains are sent to the data station through the tracks and only authenticated users are allowed to trigger a federated learning. The open source implementation of PHT, Vantage (<https://vantage6.ai/>) will be used as the software solution for performing privacy preserving federated machine learning on the datasets.

Figure 3: PHT query journey

The PHT was developed by experts at the IKNL and the University of Maastricht and has been applied in numerous oncological use-cases in the Netherlands and internationally. Selected projects include PROSPECT, a prostate cancer study, of which NKI-AvL is a collaborator; rare cancer registry developments such as RARECANnet Asia and BLUEBERRY (IKNL), the atomCAT anal cancer study (AvL-NKI).

The specific computing resources required for STRONG-AYA are outlined in the technical blueprint attached which is the evolving standard operating procedure defining the integrity and safety of the system alongside the Data Management Plan.

In the proposed federated structure, the exchange of statistical summaries and model coefficients (e.g., odds ratio) are as close as possible to anonymization without becoming unfit for the purpose of actionable insights and testable hypotheses to improve the care of AYAs with cancer. In so far as the same such statistics and results are printed in public report and articles, then the information exchanged in federated learning is NOT any more identifiable than articles and reports. Safety and integrity of the local data spaces is the responsibility of the local PI and his/her IT team. Safety and integrity of the federation cross-institutional communications networks will be the responsibility of Medical Data Works, who have been subcontracted to host the STRONG-AYA central server. The design of the software safeguards and the algorithmic integrity is a joint undertaking of UNIMAAS and IKNL.

6 Data analysis

Sample size:

As previously mentioned, since the main aim of this study is to implement the COS, no formal sample size calculation will be done and will be dependent on the specific sub-question on analysis undertaken by researchers using the STRONG AYA ecosystem

From all AYA with cancer diagnosed in the STRONG-AYA centres, we expect that the prospective part of STRONG-AYA will be available to around 4000 patients each year (please see the Table below) that will be followed longitudinally over time (each year). This number will only grow when STRONG-AYA will open in other countries. When patient inclusion for the prospective part of the data collection is not possible directly after diagnosis, it is also possible to include patients or survivors later in their patient journey (retrospective clinical practice). We will aim for a response rate of 25%.

AYA Cancer patients per institution based on historical data

Short Name	Historical numbers (retrospective)	New cases expected per year (prospective)
IRCCS	2000	400 (primary focus on sarcomas; breast, testicular and melanoma)
UL	6000	600 (all tumour types)
MU	2000	355 (primary focus on Breast, Gynaecology, Sarcoma, Germ cell, CNS)
MSCNRIO	600	150 (primary focus testicular cancers, sarcomas)
IGR	2000	800 (all tumour types)
CLB	2000	150 (all tumour types)
NKI	4000	500 (all tumour types)
YCE	12775	>1000 (all tumour types)

With regard to retrospective registries/population-based study data: As an important step towards the development of future personalised prediction models, STRONG-AYA will also utilise data from the existing databases available within its consortium (e.g. in The Netherlands: clinical data from the Netherlands Cancer Registry and patient-reported outcomes via the PROFILES registry of over 4000 AYA who were diagnosed with cancer 5-20 years ago, as well as the SURVAYA dataset (IRBd18-122); in UK: clinical data from the National Cancer Registry).

Statistical analysis:

A full data analysis plan will be developed prior to data analysis initiation and will be pre-registered in a relevant public repository (e.g. Open Science Foundation, <https://osf.io>). As the research questions applied to STRONG AYA will be highly variable, this document will be dynamic and ever-evolving.

Descriptive data analysis: prevalence/incidence poor outcomes

Summary statistics will be exchanged between centres in order to calculate prevalence/incidence rates of poor outcomes and explore cohort differences prior to modelling. Categorical variables will be compared using chi-square test, and numerical variables will be compared using a one-way ANOVA test. All tests will be carried out using summary statistics (number of patients, mean and standard deviation values) rather than individual patient data. Estimated survival / recurrence rates and potential follow-up times will be calculated by each centre individually, using the Kaplan-Meier estimator. The median follow-up time will be calculated based on the inverse Kaplan-Meier estimator. A detailed approach to handling missing values, on a within- and between-centre basis, will be specified in the data analysis plan.

Risk factors and mechanisms

Already-established predictive and prognostic factors for the outcomes in question will be identified through a systematic review of the literature. This approach identified the initial list of relevant data to be collected; this was subsequently prioritised in a Delphi study, and additional factors were added. A final plan for factor selection and model refinement will be available in the data analysis plan.

(multivariate) Linear and logistic regression analyses for continuous and dichotomous outcomes respectively, and Cox regression for time-dependent outcomes will be used. Moderation and mediation effects will be explored, depending on research question. Multivariate analyses will be adjusted for identified case-mix factors.

7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study protocol assumes standard of care is provided to AYA cancer patients, there is no clinical intervention performed by or within this protocol. Therefore, no informed patient consent is needed to collect the data described in this protocol.

Each institution will acquire separate local approvals for accessing and collecting patient data for research; the local coordinating investigator will be responsible for providing a copy of the letter confirming that use of data for research is approved (e.g. from Institution Review Board, IRB), including approval reference number.

As no individual patient data will be exchanged between institutions, no data transfer agreements or additional patient consent will be needed. However, in caution to mitigate privacy risks, a Joint controllership agreement will be drafted between all partners of the STRONG AYA consortium prior to data collection. Local information governance (IG) and data protection review of the distributed learning infrastructure may be needed, and should be obtained wherever appropriate. The study coordinators may be able to assist with supporting material.

A pan-European ROPA and DPIA has been conducted and circulated to all STRONG AYA consortium members to review and sign. It is expected to be a dynamic document that evolves with the project over time to ensure best practice regarding data security.

8 ORGANISATION AND POLICIES

Study oversight and management

Details of the consortium engagement and project management are described in detail in a collaborative research agreement and the consortium agreement. In brief, the consortium consists of the senior investigators, co-investigators, and local institutional participants. Consortium membership will be inclusive, with all individuals contributing (e.g. to local institutional work) eligible, but each centre will be asked to name a single centre lead who will take final responsibility for centre contribution.

Day-to-day management will be handled by the study coordinator, supported by the consortium leadership team (senior investigators and co-investigators). This group will meet regularly to ensure smooth study conduct and communication. The study coordinator meets with the involved parties of each work package monthly to stay on top of activities and concerns and reports weekly to the lead PIs. A detailed reference regarding the project's decision making structures, communications guidelines, quality assurance for deliverables, conflict resolution and risk management plans, as well as other policies and procedures, have been incorporated into the Project Handbook. Additional online meetings for the full consortium will provide study oversight.

As patient-centred research is a tenant of the project's objectives and ethos, a Patient Advisory Board is currently being recruited to provide patient advice on STRONG AYA's activities. This is further complimented by an Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Board and a Scientific Advisory Board to ensure that STRONG AYA does not exist in an intellectual silo and is accountable to experts in the relevant areas.

Publication policy

STRONG AYA's authorship policy follows the accepted principles for establishing authorship according to the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors which defines the four following criteria for claiming authorship:

- Substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work;
- Drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content;
- Final approval of the version to be published;
- Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

The contributions of authors should be identifiable, and authors should have confidence in the contribution of co-authors. Authorship positions and the corresponding author should be decided before the work is completed and with consensus among the parties. If conflict arises, the matter will follow the internal conflict resolution pathway. All parties listed as authors should meet all four of the criteria outlined in the ICMJE guidelines. The corresponding author should make sure that they are available throughout the submissions process to respond to editorial queries and reviewer's comments in a timely manner. The authorship criteria is not intended for use to disqualify STRONG-AYA colleagues from authorship who otherwise meet authorship criteria by denying them the opportunity to meet the second and third criteria. In addition to listing authors, all scientific publications stemming from STRONG AYA will acknowledge the consortium via the use of an

'acronym' or statement following the authorship list "...on behalf of the STRONG-AYA consortium". A full list of STRONG-AYA contributors, by institution, will be listed in the acknowledgements of publications. This list will be reviewed before publication submission to ensure it is up to date. Authors are expected to acknowledge non-academic support as well where possible, including but not limited to those who have provided materials or methods, organizational support, technical support, clinical cases, patients and their relatives, funding bodies, etc. All successful publications should be reported to the Project Coordinator for inclusion in the dissemination tracker. For the primary study publications, we plan to name the senior investigators and co-investigators, and one local lead per institution as co-authors. We will apply for a consortium "group" authorship, and within this group authorship, we will add the names of each additional person that has contributed in a meaningful way to this project, including all relevant consortium members.

Infrastructure user agreement

Medical Data Work BV (MDW, <https://medicaldataworks.nl/>) implements a privacy preserving distributed infrastructure that investigators in STRONG-AYA will use. Therefore, an Infrastructure User Agreement (soon to follow) is required as a contractual agreement between each institution and MDW, and the same agreement is required between the principal investigators and MDW.

MDW will not be considered as a "processor" of clinical data according to the definition in the EU General Data Protection Regulation, but is solely the provider of the infrastructure. As the infrastructure provider, MDW will enforce the legal use of algorithms and data stations, and this agreement shall define the terms and conditions for the use of the infrastructure.

A template Infrastructure User Agreement (from MAASTRO) will be provided to all partners in the project.

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Appendix 1: STRONG AYA Business Architecture

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

Deliverable Report

WP2– Governance, Data Security and Ethics

Deliverable D2.1

Ecosystem business architecture

Due date of deliverable: 31/03/2023

Actual submission date: 08/05/2023

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Description of Work	Version	Date
	Final Version	08/05/2023
	V1.0	21/04/2023

Description:

The initial design of the national ecosystem network, repositories and information flows, legal and ethical governance principles

Summary (max ½ page)

The STRONG AYA ecosystem business architecture outlines the initial design of the national and pan-European ecosystems and the principles that underpin them. It complements the technical infrastructure of the STRONG AYA network by setting out the ecosystem’s organisational structure.

The ecosystem business architecture outlines the mission and objectives of the project and governance principles; the legal structure and considerations required to implement the ecosystems, an abridgement of the data management and technical blueprint, the organisational structure of the ecosystems and briefly touches upon areas of further consideration for the sustainability of the ecosystems beyond the funding period (sustainability planning is part of other deliverables of the project).

It must be stressed that the ecosystem’s architecture is under development and refinement and so this report should be treated as a ‘living document’, capturing the work done to the point of submission and concepts agreed upon amongst the consortium thus far. It is anticipated that these structures will refine and evolve over the course of the project.

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Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
 2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
 3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
 4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
 5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
 6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
 7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
 8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
 9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
 10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
 11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
 12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
 13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
 14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
 15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)
- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
 - **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
 - **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
 - **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
 - **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
 - **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.
 - **Pseudonymisation**: the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific person, including patients, without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person in the context of the STRONG AYA project.

Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Data principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
COS	Core Outcome Set
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
ROPA	Records of Processing Activities
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)

1. Introduction

1.1. Background: adolescents and young adults with cancer

STRONG-AYA is a new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for adolescents and young Adults (AYA) with cancer, defined as individuals aged 15-39 years at cancer diagnosis. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. infertility, unemployment, financial problems) alongside decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe.

AYAs, who are a very important social and economic demographic group, need access to age-adjusted and high-quality healthcare. AYA care and research will benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders. Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and the economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

Defining AYAs with cancer as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis², their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴.

However, survival improvement in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors, perhaps because AYA have the highest absolute excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms⁵. AYA face some distinct challenges given that they belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Review Group. Closing the gap: Research and Care Imperatives for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer. National Institute of Health, National Cancer Institute, and Livestrong Young Adult Alliance: Bethesda, MD, USA, 2006.

³ Trama A, Botta L, Steliarova-Foucher E. Cancer Burden in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Review of Epidemiological Evidence. *Cancer J* 2018; 24: 256-266

⁴ Trama A, Botta L, Foschi R et al. Survival of European adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer in 2000-07: population-based data from EURO-CARE-5. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: 896-906.

⁵ Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of scientific literature, these unique issues are not yet fully recognised and addressed by the European health systems and AYAs with cancer are frequently underserved. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the integrated paediatric (“patient/family-centred”) care services versus dispersed (“disease-centered”) adult oncology services^{8,9,10}. Up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in society¹¹.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, given their challenges to sustain health insurance coverage¹². According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

1.2. Project aims

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be

⁶ Stark D, Bielack S, Brugieres L et al. Teenagers and young adults with cancer in Europe: from national programmes to a European integrated coordinated project. *European Journal of Cancer Care*, 25(3), 419–427.

⁷ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

⁸ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPe). *ESMO Open* 2021; 6: 100096.

⁹ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

¹⁰ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

¹¹ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

¹² Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

¹³ Saloustros E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. *Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health* 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁴ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

AYAs, as a unique socio-economic group, need access to age-adjusted and high-quality healthcare. AYA care and research will benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. Our consortium includes clinical and scientific leaders in AYA-care, data science and registries, The European Cancer Organisation (ECO), Youth Cancer Europe (YCE) and the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), building on previous initiatives and EU grants, and merging expertise with innovation. Within STRONG-AYA, we will set up a value-based healthcare research ecosystem to develop data-driven, interactive policy and visualization tools that bring, in co-creation with all stakeholders including patients, novel insights into AYA healthcare. This will require the establishment of symbiotic, independent, not-for-profit systems of working based at the local level across the five health services currently participating in STRONG AYA, as well as a pan-European ecosystem to manage the connections between them.

The ecosystem business architecture deliverable will cover the following aspects of the organisational and design aspects of the STRONG AYA ecosystems:

- The STRONG AYA vision
- Governance key principles that guide the establishment and management of the STRONG AYA ecosystems, including present and future participating ecosystems
- The legal structure underpinning the formation of the STRONG AYA network at both national and pan-European levels
- A synopsis of the data access and flows in the network
- The organisational aspects and responsibilities of the ecosystems
- A cursory sketch of how STRONG AYA ecosystems may be sustained beyond the funding period

Given the interconnected nature of the STRONG AYA's work packages, this deliverable pulls on work undertaken across several of its workflows: WP2, WP3, and WP4. It is the encapsulation of the work undertaken thus far and therefore should be viewed as a living document that will evolve over time.

2. Methods and materials

The WP2 leads, the EORTC, along with input from colleagues at the Brightlands Institute for Smart Society at Maastricht University (BISS) and the University of Leeds (UoL) designed a questionnaire to assess the local legal processes and governance contexts within each partner institution to establish an initial comprehensive understanding of what the STRONG AYA governance and legal structures should entail. This is necessary to meet the objectives of the project in terms of data delivery, technology, and impact whilst maintaining compliance.

The work package collaboratively developed questionnaires to gather information on the local institutional and national regulations, procedures and processes around data security and flows. This was then expanded upon using in depth detailed on-one-one meetings between WPLs and each individual data-contributing partner :

- The Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) based at the Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Hospital in Amsterdam
- The Marie-Sklodowska-Curie National Institute of Oncology (MSCNRIO) in Warsaw
- The Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (INT) in Milan
- Institut Gustave Roussy in Paris
- Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard in Lyon
- The Christie NHS Foundation Trust (a hospital trust affiliated with the University of Manchester) in Manchester
- The Leeds Teaching Hospital NHS Trust (a hospital trust affiliated with the University of Leeds) in Leeds

This establishes:

- What are the common elements of AYA healthcare data collected and feasibly collected by project partners (WP1)
- Consensus and preliminary Tier 1 list of minimum COS, to lay the foundation for future Delphi-style consensus on upgraded extended COS (WP1)
- Existing legal, governance and data management procedures that are already in place at partner institutions (WP2, WP3)
- the degree of understanding of federated research (data accessing) ecosystems, and how these can fit within the regulatory interpretation of the participating partners (WP2, WP3)
- the extent to which the existing research and operational infrastructures can be integrated with the STRONG AYA vision (WP3)
- level or degree of data preparedness (and hence data preparation needed) in order to establish the healthcare of AYA persons needed for this project (WP3)

In addition to this, The University of Leeds, with input from consortium members led in the conceptualisation of the ecosystem's organisational design and conducted a literature review to understand the wider context of healthcare research ecosystems and what they entail. The Maastricht University Clinical Data Science lab (UNIMAAS) led on identifying the design principles and technology blueprints required for implementing a STRONG AYA technical infrastructure. UNIMAAS and UoL are working in close alignment with the EORTC to develop the Record of Processing Activity (ROPA) and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) for the consortium as a whole. Through consultation with WPLs and use of expertise, ECO has begun mapping stakeholders for another deliverable (D4.1) which will inform the evolution of the ecosystem as it matures. This deliverable also pulls on concepts articulated in the technical blueprint created for WP3 in the context of D3.1 (Data Management Plan) and D3.3 (development of architectural blueprint). The legal principles underpinning the ecosystem architecture are broadly articulated below and will be discussed in further detail in D2.2/D2.3 (STRONG AYA information governance and ethics framework/ethics guidelines). The discussion of sustainability is in its infancy and represents some initial thoughts that will be further developed including within deliverable D4.12 (to be provided in September 2025 (M36)).

3. STRONG AYA Mission

STRONG AYA's mission is to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults (AYA) with cancer. As outlined in depth above, AYAs with cancer face age-specific issues (e.g. infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment during a whole life of cancer survivorship. In addition, there are several challenges that AYAs present to traditional research and care. AYAs are a very complex group clinically, sociologically and demographically which makes using standardised protocols very difficult. Not only are they liminal, existing sociologically between childhood and mature adulthood, but they are also experiencing rapid social, personal and economic change. The model of care and treatment protocols used for AYAs will often depend on their local context and whether they are treated in paediatric, adult or integrated/comprehensive healthcare settings. A number of challenges limit efforts to improve care and establish interventions to improve AYA quality of life. The liminality of AYAs means there is a dearth of AYA dedicated trials, their greater mobility makes it difficult to enable travel for trial access and they are less likely to have financial stability that enables leaving work for trial participation. AYAs with cancer then require a new approach that can allow researchers and clinicians to access real world insights from a large population and has the agility not only to adapt to a heterogenous study population but also to varying healthcare systems. Our federated learning ecosystems will allow us to do both.

To achieve our mission and to rectify the disparity in AYA care and research and to improve AYA outcomes across Europe, STRONG AYA is guided by the following principles:

1) Healthcare should be value-based

STRONG AYA seeks to use **data-driven insights** as a starting level of evidence to drive rapid developments in research, care and policy. AYA cancer is considered 'rare' in oncology with an incidence rate of less than 6 per 100,000 persons per year. This means that clinical experience is diluted and (for example) AYA cancer is more likely to be suspected later and diagnose at advanced stage. There are specific difficulties in conducting clinical trials for AYAs as well.¹⁵ For the studies that do exist, numbers of subjects are unavoidably small, making statistically significant findings difficult and therefore it is unclear what are the potentially actionable insights to improve healthcare. By broadening the research using novel privacy-safe approaches towards data sharing and data analytics, STRONG AYA will bring novel insights into AYA healthcare, encourage ethical re-use for scarce AYA research data, provide real-world evidence to all important AYA oncology decision-makers, and thus, increasing the benefit for patients whilst making care more efficient.

2) Access to and experience of healthcare should be consistent and transparent across Europe

As AYAs are an under-researched demographic and straddle the traditional divisions between paediatric and adult oncology, the type of or approach to care an AYA person experiences varies significantly between paediatric and adult oncological institutions, between regions, and between countries. By establishing a Core Outcome Set for AYA care and using data-driven insights gathered via our pan-European ecosystem, STRONG AYA will share insights with policy-

¹⁵ See for example, Ferrari et al (2021), Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE). *ESMO open*, 6(2), 100096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esmoop.2021.100096>; and Fern et al ((2014). Available, accessible, aware, appropriate, and acceptable: a strategy to improve participation of teenagers and young adults in cancer trials. *The Lancet. Oncology*, 15(8), e341–e350. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(14\)70113-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(14)70113-5).

makers to address and reduce inequalities across the entire disease pathway of different cancers in AYAs in different regions in Europe with an aim towards establishing a European-wide standard of care. STRONG AYA will enable AYA healthcare quality outcomes monitoring by tracking access to AYA nurse specialists, fertility consultants, and social workers for discussion about work and establish benchmarking between the different countries on key performance indicators.

3) Co-creation with stakeholders, especially patients

Clinical trials and medical research historically have been driven by the questions and concerns clinicians and researchers wish to investigate. However, it is patients who are directly impacted by the outcomes of research. Their questions and concerns should be placed on equal footing with clinical research areas of interest. By involving patients in the process of co-creation, STRONG AYA will create a platform that serves patients and empowers them. STRONG AYA will equip AYAs with cancer with the data to better optimise their healthcare, and support shared and personalised decision-making between AYA and health care providers. This also extends to the control of, access to, and use of AYA's data in the context of research and healthcare.

4) Control over data

The key enabling technologies in STRONG AYA will revolve around patients and data-gathering institutions (such as clinical registries and treating hospitals) being able to retain the task of control over their data. Asking patients and institutions to hand over their data to a centralized European repository significantly increases the "trust distance" between the person giving the data and the steward guarding the data, in effect eroding the extent of direct controllership held by the data contributor.

STRONG AYA implements a federated pan-European data access infrastructure while allowing data contributors, such as treating institutions and patient organizations, to retain direct controllership over their own data. This keeps the data private and protected against being used by anyone outside of the controlling institution. Federated integration of multi-institutional data retains local governance and control over data.

The innovation we implement within STRONG AYA is to derive data-driven healthcare insights from multiple sets of private and geographically fragmented datasets; partners UNIMAAS and IKNL in the consortium are specialist experts in this question of "federated learning" which numerous successful projects on their track record.

5) FAIR and Federated data: sharing insight with compliance

STRONG AYA follows the FAIR data management principles which means that data remains findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable even while it stays fully private under the direct control of disparate institutions. The FAIR principles will accordingly be applied at partner, national and pan-European levels for data, and subsequently digital artefacts (e.g., software, publications, reports) generated from the project work. STRONG AYA will utilize federated analytics, i.e. the performance of statistical analyses and summary visualisations of data but without transmitting any individual patient-level data outside of the data-owning institution. STRONG-AYA also supports federated learning such that prognostic and predictive (statistical) models can be developed without exchanging individual patient-level data. Privacy protection for federated analytics and federated learning is based on the unfeasibility of reverse-engineering a particular individual subject's identity from summaries, statistical models and other aggregated

results (which are typically presented for reports and publications). This means that STRONG AYA partners and stakeholders will be ethically, technically and pragmatically empowered to share insights but *not the actual* data. This allows STRONG AYA to generate new insights from aggregated data to achieve its aims, in a way that complies with national and European standards of privacy, ethics and data security.

6) Sustainable scalability: offer new opportunities without leaving anyone behind

The development of a COS for AYAs with cancer can enable STRONG AYA to offer new opportunities for the collection of prospective data that some of our participating centres have never collected before supporting new research and care innovation. Federated learning marks a new frontier in using data to solve modern health challenges. Federated learning is an agile and adaptable model that allows us to flexibly incorporate existing systems and practices into a larger ecosystem of knowledge exchange. A guiding principle of the STRONG AYA ecosystems is to accommodate local centres and their contexts whilst connecting them across Europe.

Our ecosystems are ways of working that aim:

- To generate a stronger culture of successful and sustainable working together about AYA with cancer
- To integrate 'traditional' clinical, epidemiological and data science processes with patient-centred data, patients and their groups, policy makers and others
- To speed up key analyses of data about AYA with cancer
- To improve services, experiences, and outcomes

Our ecosystems include:

- Sophisticated websites
- A set of local databases, set up in a very specific way
- Portals through which stakeholders will enter and access information
- Tools that we design and manage access to, that can optimise the knowledge gained from our local data
- Expertise required to operate the ecosystem at both the European (expert guidance) and local (clinical support, data management, and technical/IT support)

The COS and the federated infrastructure both allow STRONG AYA to scale and therefore increase its sustainable potential.

4. Governance Principles, Data Security and Ethics

4.1 General Governance - GDPR

The in-depth development of the governance principles of STRONG AYA will be completed in the first year of the project. An inventory of relevant existing ethical and governance codes and guidelines already present in the various partner institutions will result in the development of the project's ethical and legal guidelines and framework and will align principles from the different STRONG AYA partners as well as relevant EU governance and ethics principles, such as the 'European Ethical Principles for Digital Health' (2022) and key principles for data protection as laid out in the GDPR. These principles include (but are not limited to):

- Lawfulness, fairness and transparency: [data shall be] processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject);

- Purpose limitation: [data shall be] collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes;
- Data minimisation: [data shall be] adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- Accuracy: [data shall be] accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay;
- Storage limitation: [data shall be] kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject;
- Integrity and confidentiality: [data shall be] processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures;
- Accountability: The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, paragraph 1 [the previous 6 principles]).

Whilst it is premature at the time of writing (Spring 2023) to fully elaborate on each of these principles, we can expand upon some practical governance principles around data access and use in the ecosystems.

The STRONG AYA governance principles chiefly concern **how the STRONG AYA consortium defines what it will do with data and what it cannot do with data ethically and legally**. They address this at two geographical levels: the local (usually national) ecosystems and a single pan-European ecosystem.

4.2. Data protection principles and governance

1) Local data ownership and stewardship

At the pan-European level, a fundamental principle is that STRONG AYA will not take or distribute any consortium member's data nor act as its steward. Each institution is the steward of its own data and therefore must use existing safeguards and comply with local regulations and procedures to ensure the security of data held on their own machines.

2) Pseudonymisation and compliance review

The data that STRONG AYA partners will make privately accessible in a federated way will be **pseudonymised**, and the COS variables will be reviewed by data security experts to ensure that the desired COS variables are at the absolute minimum necessary to get the actionable insights that the consortium wants to achieve and not superfluous to that overall objective, according to data minimization principle (art.. 5.1.c of the GDPR).

Ethical governance of STRONG AYA data protection activities will take place through an interplay of national governance procedures (related to the five countries involved in this project), local (institutional) governance procedures and project-level governance centralized in the Strong AYA

Ethical Advisory Board. Key in this interplay is the PI of each STRONG-AYA institution, who liaises between the IRB, internal regulators and the [STRONG AYA body] about data protection and data re-use. Consortium partner expertise, as well as project-level guidance, helps PI's to convey relevant information on FAIR use linked to federated data learning to feed into the review decisions of local IRB.

At the project level, a pan-European DPIA and ROPA will be undertaken by the EORTC on behalf of STRONG AYA and the Data Management Plan (D3.1) outlines how data is to be used, protected and processes across the course of the project to ensure its compliance with European law. At the national level, the PI inside each institution must consult their IRB and internal regulators whether or not they are allowed to extract and re-use the data from their internal databases, for the STRONG AYA project. The only proviso is that the data will be pseudonymized and stored inside a machine controlled by that institution. In addition to governing the collection and processing of prospective data, an important consideration of the project is also to consider procedures of consent or compatibility assessment for secondary data use. Our centers also will need to ensure that use of retrospective data for STRONG AYA is either suitably compliant with the initial scope of previously collected consent, or to go-back and re-ask for consent again from the patient. Another possibility is a waiver from needing to do so, which is a question that each local PI has to ask their own institutional watchdog.

4.3. Patient-centred principles of ethics and governance of STRONG AYA activities, based on the 'European Ethical Principles for Digital Health'

The development of STRONG-AYA tools will be directed by the imperative of interpreting and following ethical principles that are centred on the interests and values of patients. The European Principles for Digital Health will provide the foundation that ethics research within the STRONG-AYA consortium builds upon, ensuring that the core principles are iterated and reflected in the development federated learning ecosystem, and that the iteration of these core principles also reflects the interests and values of the AYA patient group, as evidenced by stakeholder consultation and engagement. This will include working to try and meet the following ethical desiderata:

Base data-intensive STRONG AYA tools on humanistic values

1. Research and tools developed in STRONG AYA complement and optimize face-to-face healthcare.
2. Patients are informed about the benefits and limits of tools developed in STRONG AYA .
3. Patients are informed about the functioning of tools developed in STRONG AYA and can customize interactions with them.
4. When artificial intelligence is used, all reasonable efforts are made to make it explainable and without discriminatory bias, which also promotes the long-term sustainability of STRONG AYA.

Enable patients to manage their data used in the STRONG AYA tools.

5. Patients are actively involved in shaping the development and governance of STRONG AYA research and tool realization.
6. Patients can easily and reliably retrieve their health data in a commonly used format.

7. Patients can easily access information on how their health data have been or may be accessed and for which purpose.
8. Patients can easily and reliably grant access to their health data and exercise their rights.

Make STRONG AYA tools inclusive

9. Digital Health services developed in STRONG AYA are accessible by all, including by people with disabilities or low levels of (digital) literacy.
10. STRONG AYA tools are intuitive and easy to use.
11. Patients have access to training that helps them to use and understand digital health tools.
12. STRONG AYA tools are implemented in care routines that include support through human communication when needed.
13. Strong AYA is accessible and welcoming to new consortium partners and organizations in future.

4.4. Governing ethics beyond data protection

Next to issues of data protection, the STRONG AYA consortium needs to respond to ethical issues that are not easily captured in established regulations (including unanticipated questions) that will emerge while the project is ongoing. To do so, ethics guidance in STRONG AYA will be iteratively developed, steered by ethics workshops that will take place during consortium meetings, as well as through qualitative interviews with project partners. With this iterative method, STRONG-AYA aims to respond to relevant ethical and governance issues with a bottom-up approach, attending to concerns as they arise from the emerging research infrastructure and collaborative research actions.

Anticipated ethical and governance issues that will deserve specific scrutiny and guidance are, for example (this is an indicative and not an exhaustive list):

- evaluation (and capacity building) of relevant expertise with issues pertaining to federated data learning in the various partner institutions,
- guidance of 'meaningful' patient participation that leads to actionable patient-centred and patient-informed insights,
- effects of the STRONG-AYA infrastructure on lock-in and path dependency, issues pertaining to training by means of synthetic data,
- negotiating public and private (commercial) interests in data-intensive research development.

Following each consortium meeting, an interim ethics report will be submitted to an Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Board for comment. Of note, the project Ethics and Regulatory Advisory Board shall not substitute or duplicate the official Ethics Committee established according to laws. It will rather assess the direction taken by the project and the actions taken for safeguarding patient's rights and values.

The consortium will establish a governance model fulfilling STRONG-AYA needs but enabling smooth decision taking with respect to the access and use of project data (i.e. who can have access to which type of data and for doing what). WP2 partners will examine existing governance models already developed in other European research projects and which could be adapted as needed to STRONG-

AYA but also eventually updated according to the current legal, political and ethical environment. This will be described in D2.2 STRONG-AYA information/research governance and ethics framework.

5. Legal structure

There are three structural parts that will ensure that our federated learning ecosystem can operate:

- 1) There has to be a **defined consortium** with a defined purpose and defined membership, with self-enforcement and compliance powers at the consortium membership level – this is defined by the STRONG AYA consortium agreement (completed on 20 December 2022).
- 2) There has to be a **data access with joint data controllership agreement** between consortium members, which spells out :
 - a. that STRONG AYA will collect the data separately and independently at the local institutional level, obeying all local rules and regulations in operation inside each particular institution
 - b. that STRONG AYA members will each separately and independently be stewards of their own data collection, however the data they are asked to steward is not entirely free choice – the core request for data is determined for the consortium by internal consensus in the STRONG AYA consortium via the development of the Core Outcome Set.
 - c. That each consortium member will each separately and independently execute the computations and analyses on their own data, and then report back the results of the computation but we will not share any data – however the computations that run will not be free choice, it is determined as the use cases (i.e., charts and analyses and models) that are determined for the consortium from questions and challenges that patients, clinical service providers, clinicians and others identify by internal consensus within the STRONG AYA consortium
 - d. There will be access control – i.e., an institution, prior to the commencement of computations, can opt itself out of any of the above specific computations – if it finds that the computation will violate its local institutional rules regarding the usage of their data
 - e. It is joint controllership because every institution controls its own data, but by way of the establishment of the consortium, whatever the consortium agrees to compute is being “applied” to all parties by the authority willingly delegated to the leading partner of the consortium, in this case the NKI.
- 3) There has to be an **infrastructure usage agreement between each partner institution and a service company** (i.e., Medical Data Works in the case of STRONG AYA) being tasked by the consortium to carry out our secure network communications and combine the individual computational results into a combined consortium-wide result. This is a bilateral agreement between each partner with MDW, but as this has already been undertaken by the NKI on behalf of the consortium it is not a requirement to repeat this between each member of the consortium.

6. Outline of data flows and access in STRONG AYA

6.1. National / regional level (so-called grassroots level) ecosystems

Each Partner controls and operates its own national or local ecosystem. This is expected to consist of, but is not exclusively limited to, local data resources that the Partner is able to access solely by themselves as independent institutions, such as:

- research databases,
- clinical trials case reports,
- cancer registries,
- hospital-based electronic health records,
- repositories of patient (or self) reported outcomes, and
- other such databases that the Partner deems relevant for the STRONG-AYA (see Work Package 1 – Core Outcomes, for example)

These “grassroots” data sources are allowed to be either retrospective, or prospective, or a mixture of both. Since each Partner owns, controls and operates in their own space, they will autonomously decide when and which Data to make accessible for Federated Learning through the STRONG-AYA consortium.

There is no intellectual, technical or consortium-derived mandatory requirement on every Partner to make all Data completely accessible at exactly the same time; noting, as mentioned above, that the data collection paradigm must allow for dynamism, adaptability and step-by-step accumulation (and maturation) of the Data over time.

Each Partner will be responsible for requesting individual-level subject data from primary data sources within their own area of control (as above, the electronic health records, cancer registries, etc. etc.) using local governance mechanisms and technical instruments that are feasible for the Partner. These mechanisms and instruments may, for illustration purposes only, include Data Transfer Agreements between themselves and national cancer registries, and customized data extraction tools from electronic health records hosted in their local hospital (see, for a purely illustrative example, Figure 1 below).

Figure 41: STRONG AYA data flows

Existing governance and instruments should be re-used wherever possible, with a view to grow and sustainably reach a better quality of Data collection over time. For details about which data items to locate and extract, the Partners must refer to the guidance of STRONG-AYA Work Package 1.

Each Partner stores **pseudonymized** Data they have extracted from their local sources into a secured computation device which is within their institutional data security firewall. This device resides on a sub-network that can be insulated from other mission-critical and operational systems used by the institution. The Partner needs to ensure sufficient security for the private Data in their own collection, using the advice of their local data protection officers and information security teams.

If a Partner uses pseudonym keys to link information of the same human subject from multiple data sources, such key files must be **stored on a separate device** from the Data itself.

The STRONG-AYA consortium acknowledges that some Partners may already have mature technical and governance systems in place to manage these local data extractions and local data flows. Other Partners may request technical support and knowledge sharing to help set this up over the course of the Project. Such requests for technical support and knowledge sharing should not be unreasonably refused, as long as it serves the purpose of achieving the Project's objectives.

6.2. Consortium ecosystems (pan-European and national)

The pan-European federated learning ecosystem is intended, in its mature form, to empower citizens, cancer patients, healthcare providers, public institutions and private enterprises to (i) retain a governance role over their own data, (ii) partner together inside consortia that meet common goals, and (iii) have safeguards and access controls in place about what is learned from their data.

We believe that a grassroots level Data ecosystem integrated with a pan-consortium Personal Health Train implementation is one of the best-fit paradigms that achieves the above aspirations (see Figure

Figure 52: Consortium-level ecosystem at top half of figure, integrating with national/regional ecosystems championed by each Partner independently at bottom half of figure. The desired partnerships are to be built between stakeholder illustrated across the top of the figure (reads from bottom up)

2). Therefore, at the consortium level, we must provide a unifying bridge between all Partners, consisting of:

- A common technology infrastructure, supporting secure telecommunications and web-based applications/computation algorithms (see mainly Work Package 3).
- A common set of standard technical operation rules and governance guidelines that defines who is allowed to learn what insight, from which data and for what legitimate purpose (see mainly Work Package 4).

In the common technology infrastructure, the actions in the Project as a wide consortium connects with the actions of the Partner at the level of the data lake-house. Here, the Partner's Data collection needs to be made FAIR and then available for Federated Learning, using tools developed and extended within the Project among the technology Partners (Work Package 3).

In other words, STRONG AYA will be structurally composed of:

1. a pan-European and locally integrated web-based portals, which

- Provides specific access to each specific individual logging in, according to their own characteristics

- Serves multiple stakeholders
- enables a virtual desktop linkage, having access to parts of local IT systems
- The highest layer will be public – anyone finding the website can see this layer – our purpose, our achievements, our openly published reports, summaries of services we offer to others
- The next layer might be accessible to all Strong-AYA members, upon login. It might include internal policy drafts, for example, and ‘Apps’
- Another layer might be only available through a specific new request – for example an industry partner, researcher, or policy-maker wanting to commission a new analysis
- Further layers may include progressively more restricted information, as far as we want, and we are comfortable within our information security rules and systems

2. a set of databases at the local level (Data lake-houses) that:

- will store individual-patient data in a private box, or ‘safe space’ within our local systems
- will exist only according to the local regulations that we routinely use already, or that we develop locally during Strong-AYA
- will restrict access to local team members according to their permissions (unless [e.g. in one nation] permissions are given or have been given to share at a local level)

3. Portals through which stakeholders will all be able to:

- Enter information and data (that they ‘own’ ethically and legally and are permitted to enter)
- View information and data to monitor, evaluate and compare outcomes (at a level of detail that fits with their permissions)
- See relevant data summaries whether for clinical, research, service user or policy purposes, according to their permissions
- Re-use already existing institutional infrastructure and data warehouses to the maximum extent possible

4. Tools that can optimise the knowledge gained by us and others from our work

- By running predefined analyses automatically (‘in real time’, ‘on demand’, ‘on the fly’) upon our data
- By building AYA-specific aspects, into (for example):
- Utilising existing epidemiological questions (EuroCare)
- Utilising existing patient-driven questions (their websites)
- Utilising existing policy questions (ECO)

The STRONG AYA ecosystems are also made up of individuals with expertise and/or roles. Some of these roles may be held by the same or multiple members within or without the STRONG AYA consortium at a given time. These include:

1. Data providers

- Storer
- Developer
- Aggregator
- Harmonizer
- Publisher

- Register
- Data maintainer

2. Policies, laws and rules parties

- Policy makers
- Standardised and regulation parties

3. Keystone actors

- Founder

4. Service providers

- Data-as-a-service providers
- Analytics-as-a-service-providers
- Data service developer

5. Reuser

- Open data-driven organization
- Application developer
- Interpreter

6. Data intermediaries

- Data brokers
- Enablers
- Integrators
- Data extractor and transformer
- Data analyzer
- Data visualizer

7. Data user/data consumer

- Data curator
- Infrastructure provider
- Data sponsor
- Data consultant

From a practical operation perspective, the individual capabilities and experts in STRONG AYA are bifurcated at the European and local/national level. At the European level, experts guide the building and maintenance of the ecosystems, including its technical requirements (UNIMAAS, UOL), its legal and ethical frameworks (EORTC) and what data the ecosystems will be collecting and analysing (SOUTHAMPTON). At local level, operational experts are needed to ensure the ecosystems function. These include data collectors in the form of researchers, clinicians, and clinical support staff such as research nurses; Local legal and ethical experts to ensure compliance with local regulations such as DPOs and internal ethics review boards; data managers to manage the data lake houses and ensure the data is FAIR and accurate; and finally data scientists or IT technicians to maintain the functionality of the technical infrastructure.

Our culture should build a network between us, which can improve our patients' cancer outcomes. This will include:

- Working this way routinely, and finding it useful (even rewarding, or enjoyable)

- Ways to generate co-operation and connections, inter-dependence and creativity, which bring data science, clinical care, clinical research, epidemiology and service users closer together
- Ways to hold data that ensure it is clean, integrates, can be packaged, analysed, learned from and applied
- Better use and re-use of our data to generate information and expertise within and out-with Strong-AYA, rather than only moving knowledge forward in a traditional, linear manner
- Provider – to- processor - to- analyst – to – knowledge – to – policy; We will seek to reverse, change or re-order that sequence
- Ways to work together, soon and for decades to come, when using our suitable information, data and analytical results appropriately for the data and the user

7. Sustainability – initial thoughts

The sustainability of the STRONG AYA project is embedded in its way of working. Unlike traditional clinical trials, STRONG AYA is fundamentally about the development of new processes and networks to enable scientific discovery. Whilst sustainability factors for the project will be explored in greater depth in deliverables produced by WP4, it is useful here to sketch out some initial thoughts on how sustainability can be built into the STRONG AYA ecosystems. Some areas of consideration are more mature at this point than others, and this report will be updated to reflect evolving sustainability concerns as the project matures.

The first consideration is the software infrastructure sustainability. By partnering with the IKNL, the developer of the vantage6 software that operates the STRONG AYA technical infrastructure, we have a direct link to the technical operation and maturation of the software over time within the consortium itself. Moreover, the federated analytics and federated learning codes that will be built to operate STRONG AYA will be built on top of the IKNL infrastructure will be fully open source code and fully open access, given by UNIMAAS in a public software repository.

The agility and adaptation offered by the federated learning infrastructure and the approach to ways of working in STRONG AYA mean that scaling STRONG AYA technologically is straightforward and can account for the diversity of EHRs and data processes of new member institutions.

STRONG AYA is imagined to operate as a not for profit business, which means sustainability costs will be centred around expanding access to its analytics and new data lake-houses and maintaining the data managers required to ensure the technical infrastructure continues to operate after the end of the project. Given the wide range of stakeholders, this could involve a subscription service for research centres, regulatory bodies, NGOs, governments or policy makers who use STRONG AYA insights regularly, or payment by analysis or by view for more bespoke or ad-hoc use of the STRONG AYA analytics.

A greater challenge will be negotiating STRONG AYA's sustainability from a governance perspective; both with onboarding new participants and for governing the project at the end of the funding period. While it is too early yet to consider the organizational governance structure after funding, the EORTC's expansive European knowledge and establishment of best practices from the onset of the project, coupled with the successful connection of STRONG AYA's already diverse consortium will provide persuasive use-cases that will, it is hoped, assuage data security concerns and contribute positively to the European Digital Health Space agenda. Furthermore, other members of the STRONG AYA consortium are involved in other European projects tackling similar concerns, such as the [JANE](#)

project led by the Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori, offering STRONG AYA expertise and the opportunity to synergise with other European projects.

8. Conclusion/ next steps

This document summarises key components of the ecosystem business architecture for STRONG AYA. The development of the ecosystems' infrastructure is ongoing and as such, this document represents the alignment achieved thus far on the governance and technical aspects of the ecosystem and the consortium's progress to date. It should therefore be treated as a 'living document', capturing the work done to the point of submission and concepts agreed upon amongst the consortium thus far. It is anticipated that these structures will refine and evolve over the course of the project.

The STRONG AYA ecosystem business architecture outlines the initial design of the national and pan-European ecosystems and the principles that underpin them. It complements the technical infrastructure of the STRONG AYA network by setting out the ecosystem's organisational structure. The document summarises the mission and objectives of the project and governance principles; the legal structure and considerations required to implement the ecosystems, an abridgement of the data management and technical blueprint, the organisational structure of the ecosystems and briefly touches upon areas of further consideration for the sustainability of the ecosystems beyond the funding period (sustainability planning is part of other deliverables of the project).

It is supplementary to other deliverables of the project. The management of data is more exhaustively defined in the first Data Management Plan (D3.1, already submitted at time of writing in M6) with a final version due at the end of the project. The technical requirements are discussed in further depth in the evolving technical blue print (D3.3 – due M12). The governance and ethics framework is being developed in D2.2 (expected M12). The operational plans of the ecosystems, both local/national and pan-European, are deliverables 4.4, 4.6, 4.7 (due M9 and M12). Sustainability planning is the focus of D4.12 (M36), and D4.15 (54). will continue throughout the life of the project.